

SHORT-FIBRE/TITANIUM-MATRIX COMPOSITES

S.T.Mileiko, M.V.Gelachov, A.A.Khvostunkov, V.M.Kiiko, and D.B.Skvortsov
Solid State Physics Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences
Chernogolovka Moscow distr., 142 432 Russia

ABSTRACT

Preliminary results of the experiments with titanium alloys and chopped carbon fibres as raw materials used in a powder metallurgy process are presented. A variety of the particular fabrication routes has been tried (sintering in vacuum and in a HIP process, special heat treatments, various blending procedures, etc). The microstructure analyzed by optical microscopy and X-ray patterns supplies the information on both spatial distribution of fibres and formation of titanium carbide on the fibre/matrix interface depending on fabrication parameters. Data on the elastic characteristics, tensile and bending strength, fracture toughness, and creep properties are obtained and analyzed.

INTRODUCTION

An obvious necessity of light structural materials for temperature interval above that covered by polymer and aluminum matrix composites and below that covered by heat resistant alloys calls for titanium matrix composites. The difficulties arose when making titanium matrix composites are also obvious. They associate with the chemical reactivity of titanium at high temperature. It has brought the development of a special kind of *SiC* fibres with a surface layer enriched with carbon [1]. This solves the problem of obtaining *SiC/Ti* composites with attractive properties.

On the other hand, an attempt to use a cheaper fabrication route, casting technology being an example, to produce carbon-fibre/titanium-matrix composites are known [2]. However, to reduce the melting temperature of the matrix in order to decrease a thickness of the interface zone composed of titanium carbide, one has to have the copper content as high as 70%. So the product may hardly be considered as a carbon-fibre/titanium-matrix composite.

At the Solid State Physics Institute an attempt to use liquid phase fabrication route in a different fashion was undertaken [3]. The method is based on introducing carbon fibres into titanium matrix through an interphase of a titanium/titanium-silicide eutectic with the melting point about 1330°C. The eutectic infiltrates either the fibre bundle or fibre layer. The process takes a time of some seconds, so a relatively thin titanium carbide layer is formed at the fibre/eutectic interface. A choice of the fibre type determines the infiltration time, and the matrix determines mechanical properties of the composites at room and elevated temperatures.

Powder metallurgy methods of fabricating composites using carbon fibres and titanium powder as raw materials are expected to promise some positive results if one does not aim at a pure carbon/titanium composite. The aim should certainly be to find possibilities to make use of materials containing rather large quantities of titanium carbide. Therefore, one needs to investigate de-

dependencies of various mechanical properties of such composites on the carbide content and then see what kind of structures can be effectively used in particular applications.

FABRICATION

A routine powder metallurgy scheme shown in Fig.1 is used to produce specimens of three various shapes, those being discs, cylinders and plates.

Figure 1. Flow chart of making composites.

Blending is done in a ball mill. Cold pressing is performed in a closed die, and the corresponding dimension decreases by about a half of the original value. Certainly, this causes a definite texture of the future composite. Sintering disc specimens is done by hot pressing in a closed die under uniaxial external load. The cylinders and plates being enveloped in steel cans are sintered in a hot isostatic process.

After sintering, composites may be heat treated to produce titanium carbide layer at the fibre/matrix interface. A possibility to use rolling or extrusion after sintering to enhance the texture exists but has not been examined yet.

In most experiments, a commercial pure titanium powder was used. In some experiments, titanium alloys VT-23 and VT-6 (according to a Russian specification) were used. In all specimens high modulus carbon fibre KULON (Russian Trade Mark) was used.

MICROSTRUCTURE

First, it should be noted that at the present stage of the work, the authors' intention was to establish the dependencies of composite properties on technological and structural parameters. Technological parameters of importance are blending regimes, the direction of pressure application and the pressure value at the cold pressing stage; vacuum or no vacuum at the enveloping stage, temperature, time and pressure at the sintering stage (hipping or hot pressing), temperature - time conditions at the heat treatment stage.

Structural parameters of the primary importance are the average fibre volume fraction and spatial distribution of fibres, preferable orientation of the fibre carcass, the carbide content on the fibre/matrix interface. The carbon content is revealed by the X-ray patterns (Fig.2), however, this does not yield quantitative evaluation. Neither yields optical microscopy that shows just

qualitative picture. X-ray microanalysis, also performed in the framework of the present work, definitely shows a large change in the stoichiometry along the thickness of the carbide layer. Note also a difference between the two X-ray patterns shown in Fig.2. Two specimens differ from each other by the fibre volume fraction as well as by heat treatment temperatures. One can see that under the heat treatment conditions used, the visual quantities of the carbide are just to occur.

Figure 2. Typical X-ray patterns of C/Ti composites.

The material density as a function of the heat treatment regime is presented in Fig.3. These data can be used to evaluate approximately a dependence of the carbide content on heat treatment regime. We have the density, γ , of a composite containing graphite (C), titanium carbide (TiC) and titanium (Ti) as

$$\gamma = \gamma_C v_C + \gamma_{TiC} v_{TiC} + \gamma_{Ti} v_{Ti}$$

where a subscript relates the density and volume fraction values to a corresponding component. Volume fractions are obviously

$$v_C = v_f^o \left(\frac{d}{d_o} \right)^2 \quad v_{TiC} = v_f^o \frac{(d + \delta)^2 - d^2}{d_o^2} \quad v_{Ti} = 1 - v_f^o \left(\frac{d + \delta}{d_o} \right)^2$$

where v_f^o is the initial value of fibre volume fraction, d_o , d , and δ are the initial and current carbon fibre diameter and the carbide layer thickness, respectively. Assuming carbide being stoi-

chiometric within the layer (actually it is not so), we find [3] a relationship between values d and δ governed by the equation

$$\lambda d^2 + 2d\delta + (\delta^2 - \lambda d_0^2) = 0$$

where $\lambda = \gamma_C / \gamma_{TiC}$. Note that $d + \delta < d_0$. Therefore, the current diameter of carbon core and the thickness of the carbide layer are given by a solution of the system of algebraic equations

$$\begin{aligned} (\omega - \mu) - \omega v_f^o (\bar{d} - \bar{\delta})^2 + v_f^o (\lambda \bar{d}^2 + \bar{\delta}^2 + 2\bar{d}\bar{\delta}) &= 0 \\ \lambda \bar{d}^2 + \bar{\delta}^2 + 2\bar{d}\bar{\delta} - \lambda &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

where $\bar{d} = d/d_0$, $\bar{\delta} = \delta/d_0$, $\omega = \gamma_C / \gamma_{TiC}$, $\mu = \gamma / \gamma_{TiC}$, and $\lambda = \gamma / \gamma_{TiC}$.

The calculated data in Fig.3 were obtained for $d_0 = 8 \mu$, $\gamma_C = 1.9 \text{ g/cm}^3$, $\gamma_{TiC} = 4.92 \text{ g/cm}^3$, and $\gamma_{Ti} = 4.51 \text{ g/cm}^3$.

Figure 3. Measured density of the C/TiC/Ti composite (initial fibre volume fraction is 10%) and calculated carbide layer thickness versus heat treatment time. The sintering time/temperature pattern is 60 min/850°C. The blank was encapsulated without vacuum. The heat treatment temperature is 1075°C.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Some illustrative results of measuring elastic properties, room temperature strength and fracture toughness, elevated temperature strength and creep properties will be here presented in connection with the technological parameters.

ELASTIC CHARACTERISTICS

The dependencies of the elastic modulus on heat treatment regimes are shown in Fig.4. The elastic modulus was obtained by using the ultrasonic pulse technique. To exclude an effect of

Figure 4.

- (a) Dynamic modulus of heat treated *C/TiC/Ti* composites normalized by that of the same composites before heat treatment versus initial fibre volume fraction. The heat treatment time and temperature are 60 min and 1075°C.
- (b) Normalized dynamic modulus of *C/TiC/Ti* composites (initial fibre volume fraction is 10%) heat treated at 1075°C versus heat treatment time. Both sets of the specimens were obtained under sintering conditions as shown in Fig.3.

It should be noted that the initial elastic modulus of randomly three-dimensionally reinforced *C/Ti* composites is lower than that of the titanium matrix since the spatially averaged Young's modulus of graphite is known to be about 70 GPa which is less than that of titanium (≈ 110 GPa). The data presented show a possibility to enhance the elastic modulus of *C/Ti* composites by introducing into the composite structure the *TiC* ingredient. It would of interest to obtain a solution of the problem of the elastic behaviour of a composite with three-dimensional system of composite fibres consisting of anisotropic graphite core and isotropic outer layer.

STRENGTH AND FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The failure behaviour of the composites under consideration is effected by a variety of the technological parameters that influence the microstructure specified above. Being limited in the space, we are to present here some characteristic dependencies only (Figs. 5 to 8).

One can see that

1. A strength maximum for such composites can be observed at very low fibre volume fractions (about 5%). At elevated temperatures the point of the maximum strength shifts to higher values of v_f^o .
2. The blending of the raw mixture, which homogenizes the mixture and, on the same time, changes the histogram of the fibre lengths, results in a non-monotonic mixing-time/strength dependence.
3. Sintering blended mixtures in vacuum produces composites with essentially higher strength than doing this procedure without vacuum.

The first observation has obvious physical reasons from the viewpoint of a micromechanical model [4]. Namely, extremely nonhomogeneous fibre packing leads to a transition from the failure mechanism based on the fibre breaks accumulation to that based on instability of the characteristic microcracks at low fibre volume fractions. Making the fibre packing more homogeneous by increasing blending time can lead to a decrease in the composite strength due to a decrease in the average fibre length. The situation is analyzed elsewhere [5]. It should be also noted that at elevated temperatures, the critical fibre volume fraction is not so low, certainly because of an increase in the matrix crack resistance with temperature increasing.

Figure 5. Bending strength versus fibre volume fraction for composites with pure titanium matrix sintered in vacuum and tensile strength at elevated temperatures versus fibre volume fraction for the same composites.

Figure 6. Tensile strength at 593°C versus fibre volume fraction for composites with titanium alloy matrices sintered in vacuum.

Figure 7. Fracture toughness of composites with pure titanium matrix versus fibre volume fraction. Composites were sintered without vacuum.

Fracture behaviour of the composites is also characterized by a maximum on the fracture-toughness/fibre-volume-fraction curve (Fig.7). To range the composites under consideration within engineering materials, we can use the plot presented in Fig.9, which is a set of the ex-

perimental data for titanium and aluminum alloys on the strength - fracture toughness plane. One can see that the room temperature fracture properties of the composites are rather close to the properties of high strength titanium alloys.

CREEP

The most important feature of the creep behaviour of the composiaviour of the composites is heat treatment, performed after a specimen crept for some time. This is shown in Fig.10. One can see that a ratio of applied stresses corresponding to equal creep rates can more than 2. The creep resistance is certainly very much dependent on the thickness of the carbide layer.

Figure 8. Bending strength at room temperature versus blending time. Sintering temperature is 900°C, sintering time is 30 min. Container enveloping without pumping out.

Figure 9. Strength - fracture toughness correlation for titanium and aluminium alloys. The data are compiled after [6]. The data for composites under consideration are located in the rectangular area shown.

CONCLUSIONS

At the present time we may formulate preliminary results only. They are as follows:

- The elastic properties of composites are essentially influenced by the fabrication regime via formation of titanium carbide phase.
- In general, the room temperature fracture properties of the composites are slightly lower than those for high strength titanium alloys. Although, improvements in the fabrication technology can lead to an essential enhancement of the room temperature strength and fracture toughness.
- At the present stage of the development, short-time high-temperature strength of the composites commences to overcome that of titanium alloys at about 700 - 800°C provided titanium alloys are used as matrix materials.
- Specific creep strength appears to be better than that of ordinary titanium alloys.

Figure 10. Short-time creep curves of C/TiC/Ti composites. The creep tests were being interrupted by heat treatments shown in the fields. The values of the stress are also shown.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The work was partially supported by the Russian Foundation for Fundamental Research under grant 93-013-16742. A part of the work was done in a research group of the Russian Composite Society.

REFERENCES

1. Y. LePeticorps, R. Pailler & R. Naslain, *Compos. Sci. & Technol.* **35**, 207-214 (1989).
2. B. Toloui, B., In *ICCM-5*, Eds. W.C. Harrigan, Jr., J. Strife, and A.K. Dhingra, (AIME, New York, 1985) pp. 773-777.
3. S.T. Mileiko, A.M. Rudnev, and M.V. Gelachov, Carbon-fibre/titanium-silicide-interphase/titanium-matrix composites - fabrication, structure and mechanical properties, *Compos. Sci. & Technol.*, in press.
4. S.T. Mileiko, In *Fabrication of Composites*, Eds. A. Kelly and S.T. Mileiko (North-Holland, Amsterdam), 1983, pp. 221 - 294.
5. S.T. Mileiko, A.A. Khvostunkov, V.M. Kiiko, and M.V. Gelachov, *Theor. Appl. Fracture Mech.*, in press.
6. S.E. Kovchik and E.M. Morozov, *Characteristics of Short Time Fracture Toughness of Materials and Methods of Their Evaluation*, (Naukova Dumka, Kiev, 1988) in Russian.